

1 **Supplementary Information for:**
2 **Benefits and Limits of Phasing Alleles for Network Inference of Allopolyploid Complexes**

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14 **Supplementary Figures**

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16 **Figure S1 — Generalized PATÉ workflow.** PATÉ is focused on calling variants and recovering
 17 phased haplotype sequences for arbitrary ploidy levels.

Key to triples

D. campyloptera

A = *D. campyloptera*

B = *D. expansa*

C = *D. intermedia*

D. celsa

A = *D. celsa*

B = *D. goldiana*

C = *D. ludoviciana*

D. clintoniana

A = *D. clintoniana*

B = *D. cristata*

C = *D. goldiana*

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20 **Figure S2 — Network hypotheses for three-species analyses with marginal likelihoods.**

21 Numbers indicate model numbers from main text figures and tables. Model five is the correct

22 one based on available evidence in *Dryopteris*. Only one ϕ parameter is estimated because the

23 other branch is constrained to $1 - \phi$.

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25 **Figure S3 — Proportion of simulations that correctly detect one reticulation.** The x-axis is

26 the number of loci and the y-axis is the proportion of correct networks. Networks are scored as

27 correct if the best network is determined to have one reticulation based on at least a two-unit

28 pseudologlikelihood increase over no reticulations and no more than a two-unit

29 pseudologlikelihood improvement for including two reticulations.

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33 **Figure S4 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.001$ and $\theta =$**

34 τ_h . The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured

35 in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated

36 values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100

37 replicates.

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40 **Figure S5 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.001$ and $\theta =$**

41 **$2\tau_h$.** The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

42 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

43 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

44 across 100 replicates.

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47 **Figure S6 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.001$ and $\theta =$**

48 **$3\tau_h$.** The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

49 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

50 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

51 across 100 replicates.

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54 **Figure S7 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.001$ and $\theta =$**

55 **$4\tau_h$.** The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

56 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

57 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

58 across 100 replicates.

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61 **Figure S8 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.01$ and $\theta = \tau_h$.**

62 The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured in
 63 the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated
 64 values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100
 65 replicates.

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68 **Figure S9 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.001$ and $\theta =$**

69 **$2\tau_h$.** The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

70 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

71 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

72 across 100 replicates.

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75 **Figure S10 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.01$ and $\theta =$**

76 $3\tau_h$. The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

77 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

78 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

79 across 100 replicates.

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82 **Figure S11 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.01$ and $\theta =$**

83 **$4\tau_h$.** The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are

84 measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true

85 simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged

86 across 100 replicates.

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89 **Figure S12 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.1$ and $\theta = \tau_h$.**

90 The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured in
 91 the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated
 92 values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100
 93 replicates.

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Figure S13 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.1$ and $\theta = 2\tau_h$.

The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100 replicates.

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Figure S14 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.1$ and $\theta = 3\tau_h$.

The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100 replicates.

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Figure S15 — Divergence Time Estimation for Species Network with $\tau_h = 0.1$ and $\theta = 4\tau_h$.

The y-axis is divergence time for each individual parameter. Divergence times are measured in the expected number of substitutions per site. The dashed line represents the true simulated values. Points are posterior means and error bars are 95% HPD intervals, averaged across 100 replicates.

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 122 **Figure S16 — Median Node Heights between MCMC Chains.** Scatterplots show the median
 123 divergence time parameters in substitutions per site between MCMC chains one and two versus
 124 three and four for each data type and triplet. Adherence of data points to the dashed one-to-one
 125 line indicates convergence, at least for divergence times.

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127 **Figure S17 — SNaQ Networks for *Dryopteris*.** Networks are the same as Figure 7, but
 128 identifiable branch lengths are shown in black next to edges. Note that terminal branch lengths
 129 are not identifiable. Introgression probabilities for the minor (hybrid) edges are shown in tan
 130 while the major edge is shown in blue.

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Figure S18 — Quartet Concordance Factors for Allopolyploids and their Parents. Taxa

133 abbreviations on the y-axis are the focal allopolyloid in a quartet. Quartets are displayed here
 134 only if they include both parents. The x-axis is the fourth member of the quartet that is a non-
 135 parent (NP). Bars are concordance factors for the proportion of quartets across all genes that
 136 the focal allopolyloid is sister to one of its parents or the non-parent. Non-ILS patterns are
 137 observable when the two minor quartets are not approximately equal, but not all patterns are
 138 reconciled in the networks. Spectra are similar between phased and unphased data
 139 (consensus).

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141 **Figure S19 — Gene Tree Discordance with Consensus Sequences.** Supported splits either
 142 in agreement or in conflict with the ASTRAL species tree from phased data was determined by
 143 a standard bootstrap proportion of 70% or greater.

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145 **Figure S20 — Gene Tree Discordance with Genotype Sequences.** Supported splits either in
 146 agreement or in conflict with the ASTRAL species tree from phased data was determined by a
 147 standard bootstrap proportion of 70% or greater.

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149 **Figure S21 — Gene Tree Discordance with Pick One Sequences.** Supported splits either in
 150 agreement or in conflict with the ASTRAL species tree from phased data was determined by a
 151 standard bootstrap proportion of 70% or greater. The hot-pink numbers next to nodes are node
 152 numbers that correspond to Supplementary Figure S22.

Data Type — consensus — genotype — pickone

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 154 **Figure S22 — Frequency of Informative and Uninformative Splits across Nodes and Data**
 155 **Types.** Phased data are not shown because such conflict analyses are not possible with
 156 multiple alleles per species without genome-scale haplotype phasing.

157 **Supplementary Tables**

ID	Species	Collector	Voucher	Ploidy	SRA
B087-A08	<i>Dryopteris campyloptera</i>	EB Sessa	EBS019	4	SRS8770054
B087-D08	<i>Dryopteris campyloptera</i>	EB Sessa	EBS022	4	SRS8770074
B125-H06	<i>Dryopteris campyloptera</i>	EB Sessa	Duke catalog 8252	4	SRS8770073
B087-A09	<i>Dryopteris carthusiana</i>	EB Sessa	EBS042	4	SRS8770079
B087-C08	<i>Dryopteris carthusiana</i>	EB Sessa	EBS041	4	SRS8770066
B124-B11	<i>Dryopteris carthusiana</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 1576	4	SRS8770067
B087-G08	<i>Dryopteris celsa</i>	EB Sessa	EBS027	4	SRS8770077
B087-H08	<i>Dryopteris celsa</i>	EB Sessa	EBS049	4	SRS8770078
B124-E12	<i>Dryopteris celsa</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 94-2	4	SRS8770071
B087-B09	<i>Dryopteris clintoniana</i>	EB Sessa	8632b	6	SRS8770080
B087-C09	<i>Dryopteris clintoniana</i>	EB Sessa	EBS016	6	SRS8770056
B095-B12	<i>Dryopteris clintoniana</i>	W Testo	Testo 591	6	SRS8770062
B087-E09	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	EB Sessa	EBS068 - D	4	SRS8770058
B087-F09	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	EB Sessa	EBS051	4	SRS8770059
B124-C12	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 33902	4	SRS8770069
B087-D09	<i>Dryopteris expansa</i>	EB Sessa	EBS030	2	SRS8770057
B124-B12	<i>Dryopteris expansa</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 23335	2	SRS8770068
B125-D06	<i>Dryopteris expansa</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa catalog 3576437	2	SRS8770072
B087-G09	<i>Dryopteris goldiana</i>	EB Sessa	EBS062	2	SRS8770060
B087-E08	<i>Dryopteris intermedia</i>	EB Sessa	EBS069	2	SRS8770075
B087-F08	<i>Dryopteris intermedia</i>	EB Sessa	EBS013	2	SRS8770076
B124-E11	<i>Dryopteris intermedia</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 594	2	SRS8770070
B087-H09	<i>Dryopteris ludoviciana</i>	EB Sessa	EBS048	2	SRS8770061
B124-A12	<i>Dryopteris ludoviciana</i>	EB Sessa	Sessa Catalog 4097	2	SRS8770065
B98-A1	<i>Polystichum munitum</i>	CJ Rothfels	4555	2	SRS8770063
B98-G1	<i>Polystichum speciosissimum</i>	MA Sundue	1712	2	SRS8770064

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159 **Table S1 – Individuals included in study.**

ID	Species	# Loci	# Variable Loci	# Invariable Loci	# Phased Loci	Locus Length	# Variants	Het	# Phased Blocks [†]	Longest Block [‡]	Number of Unique Phased Alleles					
											1*	2	3	4	5	6
B087-A08	<i>D. campyloptera</i>	404	357	47	308	518.58	5.30	0.0104	1.03	6.69	96	51	109	148	NA	NA
B087-B08	<i>D. goldiana</i>	403	258	145	199	1165.57	7.02	0.0064	1.02	13.81	204	199	NA	NA	NA	NA
B087-C08	<i>D. carthusiana</i>	408	337	71	289	1249.54	9.92	0.0086	1.02	13.71	119	43	88	158	NA	NA
B087-D08	<i>D. campyloptera</i>	121	62	59	50	564.39	7.34	0.0133	1.00	17.50	71	8	8	34	NA	NA
B087-E08	<i>D. intermedia</i>	407	200	207	120	622.50	2.52	0.0037	1.01	7.74	287	120	NA	NA	NA	NA
B087-F08	<i>D. intermedia</i>	403	178	225	124	609.41	2.36	0.0036	1.04	7.02	279	124	NA	NA	NA	NA
B087-G08	<i>D. celsa</i>	409	376	33	366	802.90	10.61	0.0138	1.01	11.77	43	40	112	214	NA	NA
B087-H08	<i>D. celsa</i>	409	375	34	365	944.28	11.95	0.0133	1.01	13.33	44	42	100	223	NA	NA
B087-A09	<i>D. carthusiana</i>	408	379	29	370	845.50	13.15	0.0163	1.01	14.45	38	34	106	230	NA	NA
B087-B09	<i>D. clintoniana</i>	409	402	7	396	569.66	12.83	0.0230	1.01	13.21	13	7	20	38	116	215
B087-C09	<i>D. clintoniana</i>	410	390	20	380	927.59	21.64	0.0237	1.01	23.31	30	5	10	26	68	271
B087-D09	<i>D. expansa</i>	399	121	278	77	501.36	1.65	0.0032	1.01	7.90	322	77	NA	NA	NA	NA
B087-E09	<i>D. cristata</i>	409	394	15	389	728.63	16.39	0.0236	1.01	17.20	20	9	42	338	NA	NA
B087-F09	<i>D. cristata</i>	409	374	35	366	813.84	15.67	0.0201	1.01	17.45	43	30	96	240	NA	NA
B087-G09	<i>D. goldiana</i>	410	108	302	79	961.39	2.29	0.0025	1.01	11.37	331	79	NA	NA	NA	NA
B087-H09	<i>D. ludoviciana</i>	410	184	226	105	1010.95	2.93	0.0030	1.02	10.57	305	105	NA	NA	NA	NA
B095-B12	<i>D. clintoniana</i>	412	395	17	384	839.66	19.22	0.0233	1.01	20.55	28	6	14	26	72	266
B98-A1	<i>P. munitum</i>	409	320	89	251	951.47	6.01	0.0065	1.01	9.46	158	251	NA	NA	NA	NA
B98-G1	<i>P. speciosissimum</i>	406	187	219	108	785.40	3.37	0.0041	1.02	11.81	298	108	NA	NA	NA	NA
B124-A12	<i>D. ludoviciana</i>	405	139	266	91	795.13	2.51	0.0034	1.00	10.63	314	91	NA	NA	NA	NA
B124-B11	<i>D. carthusiana</i>	405	399	6	390	597.90	10.36	0.0177	1.00	10.72	15	19	75	296	NA	NA
B124-B12	<i>D. expansa</i>	404	153	251	97	623.04	2.71	0.0042	1.00	10.67	307	97	NA	NA	NA	NA
B124-C12	<i>D. cristata</i>	405	388	17	377	624.96	11.61	0.0190	1.00	12.43	28	33	107	237	NA	NA
B124-E11	<i>D. intermedia</i>	405	245	160	179	856.78	4.28	0.0049	1.01	9.21	226	179	NA	NA	NA	NA
B124-E12	<i>D. celsa</i>	407	391	16	373	709.76	9.53	0.0138	1.01	10.32	34	35	102	236	NA	NA
B125-D06	<i>D. expansa</i>	395	190	205	117	381.70	2.19	0.0053	1.00	6.72	278	117	NA	NA	NA	NA
B125-H06	<i>D. campyloptera</i>	390	364	26	344	709.58	7.90	0.0113	1.01	8.88	46	45	120	179	NA	NA

[†] The average number of haplotype blocks recovered for each locus where a haplotype block exists - not all loci have phased haplotype blocks

[‡] The average number of variants per haplotype block. When more than one block per locus, only the phased variants of the longest block were retained

* One allele may not be strictly homozygous and thus the counts are higher than the number of invariable loci

160 **Table S2 – Per-individual Phasing Statistics.**

Locus	Phased Sequences			Consensus Sequences			Genotype Sequences			Pick One Sequences		
	# Seqs	# Sites	# PI Sites	# Seqs	# Sites	# PI Sites	# Seqs	# Sites	# PI Sites	# Seqs	# Sites	# PI Sites
L1	84	1469	324	25	1456	61	25	1442	58	25	1469	65
L100	84	1280	543	25	1303	232	25	1300	221	25	1276	220
L101	84	1301	457	25	1292	243	25	1304	247	25	1350	222
L102	80	1397	476	24	1330	253	24	1332	245	24	1335	253
L103	84	1659	575	25	1659	101	25	1659	100	25	1683	103
L105	84	1251	274	25	1240	84	25	1247	81	25	1247	85
L107	84	1997	568	25	2007	184	25	2007	183	25	2018	178
L11	84	1692	666	25	1722	182	25	1726	157	25	1760	166
L112	84	1957	525	25	1885	123	25	1885	153	25	1949	101
L113	84	1995	450	25	1992	138	25	1992	135	25	1993	151
L114	84	1559	792	25	1659	385	25	1536	379	25	1454	407
L115	84	1674	604	25	1703	165	25	1652	165	25	1705	183
L116	84	1794	382	25	1777	84	25	1764	95	25	1764	98
L117	84	1294	363	25	1294	62	25	1294	61	25	1294	68
L118	84	3398	894	25	3333	370	25	3332	362	25	3285	375
L12	82	1696	639	24	1682	242	24	1714	234	24	1727	256
L121	84	1460	455	25	1462	98	25	1462	96	25	1458	98
L123	84	1491	554	25	1496	214	25	1496	199	25	1486	246
L125	84	2009	611	25	1884	192	25	2026	181	25	2005	195
L127	84	1630	469	25	1645	77	25	1713	70	25	1709	70
L129	84	1663	782	25	1630	320	25	1729	264	25	1700	285
L130	84	1584	493	25	1583	117	25	1583	107	25	1583	108
L131	84	1589	423	25	1589	79	25	1589	78	25	1589	78
L132	84	1398	460	25	1398	93	25	1398	90	25	1393	90
L133	84	1323	478	25	1322	117	25	1322	113	25	1322	113
L135	84	1643	492	25	1639	80	25	1639	82	25	1644	77
L137	84	1214	463	25	1223	118	25	1214	141	25	1216	131
L138	84	1912	295	25	1911	82	25	1911	82	25	1910	84
L139	84	1421	637	25	1328	174	25	1338	167	25	1436	166
L14	84	1435	391	25	1431	128	25	1431	128	25	1429	111
L140	82	1375	655	24	1414	231	24	1316	261	24	1408	219
L141	84	1272	307	25	1270	119	25	1273	112	25	1274	72
L142	84	1531	618	25	1543	115	25	1543	119	25	1520	115
L143	84	1701	615	25	1716	159	25	1716	174	25	1767	219
L144	84	1364	715	25	1425	261	25	1426	244	25	1452	218
L145	84	1424	562	25	1410	125	25	1365	138	25	1419	152
L146	84	1727	441	25	1731	94	25	1726	92	25	1722	107
L147	84	1368	506	25	1384	81	25	1376	78	25	1385	83
L148	84	1378	522	25	1353	141	25	1311	131	25	1359	143
L149	84	1240	594	25	1289	140	25	1289	140	25	1289	117
L15	84	1524	254	25	1496	85	25	1527	86	25	1509	95
L151	84	1450	581	25	1211	294	25	1320	277	25	1346	305
L152	84	1745	581	25	1740	158	25	1736	158	25	1746	128
L154	84	1384	416	25	1374	117	25	1375	124	25	1374	127
L155	84	1690	458	25	1702	134	25	1702	133	25	1687	140
L157	84	1608	395	25	1613	84	25	1605	71	25	1605	82
L159	80	1569	541	24	1569	111	24	1569	111	24	1569	90
L161	84	1471	444	25	1471	140	25	1499	138	25	1471	153
L163	84	1919	708	25	1882	413	25	1888	385	25	1889	363
L164	84	1183	390	25	1183	60	25	1183	60	25	1183	62
L165	70	1177	370	20	1130	132	20	1065	187	20	1098	179
L166	84	1112	431	25	1113	93	25	1113	92	25	1113	100
L167	82	1398	481	24	1413	104	24	1413	102	24	1413	108
L168	84	1462	353	25	1458	96	25	1464	98	25	1464	99
L169	84	1576	719	25	1581	257	25	1653	234	25	1654	251
L17	84	1369	442	25	1369	69	25	1369	69	25	1368	67
L170	84	1541	833	25	1513	264	25	1563	237	25	1504	263
L171	84	1352	612	25	1338	180	25	1398	171	25	1287	206
L172	84	1642	509	25	1595	130	25	1594	132	25	1590	129
L173	84	1416	512	25	1423	123	25	1416	115	25	1423	138
L174	80	1329	341	24	1329	83	24	1329	82	24	1329	81

L175	84	1537	452	25	1527	182	25	1523	173	25	1534	186
L177	84	1562	753	25	1566	312	25	1584	320	25	1585	289
L179	84	1602	583	25	1568	153	25	1561	142	25	1581	160
L18	84	1988	738	25	1942	208	25	1953	218	25	1899	256
L181	82	1758	569	24	1718	144	24	1726	159	24	1719	149
L182	30	1238	299	10	1238	48	10	1238	49	10	1238	54
L183	84	1634	549	25	1645	162	25	1647	156	25	1657	164
L184	84	1153	291	25	1157	132	25	1153	131	25	1153	128
L185	84	1353	528	25	1412	199	25	1420	192	25	1231	127
L186	84	1500	529	25	1410	221	25	1411	213	25	1410	244
L187	84	1338	685	25	1332	210	25	1281	225	25	1240	217
L188	84	1013	282	25	1028	83	25	1026	87	25	1029	81
L189	84	1295	365	25	1288	149	25	1240	152	25	1277	153
L19	84	1876	1024	25	2038	516	25	1916	462	25	2001	426
L191	84	1550	349	25	1520	91	25	1522	88	25	1513	90
L193	84	1704	566	25	1706	131	25	1673	116	25	1681	134
L194	84	1727	683	25	1735	166	25	1758	160	25	1838	155
L196	84	1535	575	25	1489	124	25	1553	107	25	1494	127
L197	84	1693	758	25	1642	460	25	1729	411	25	1678	420
L198	84	1392	494	25	1393	88	25	1404	85	25	1402	93
L199	82	1408	571	24	1426	182	24	1407	194	24	1408	201
L2	80	1473	389	24	1461	95	24	1463	92	24	1453	88
L20	84	1544	702	25	1541	263	25	1504	306	25	1476	281
L200	84	1411	485	25	1472	86	25	1432	78	25	1471	77
L201	84	1715	726	25	1682	257	25	1620	258	25	1668	253
L202	84	3334	686	25	3315	281	25	3322	303	25	3240	291
L203	80	1242	284	24	1245	56	24	1242	63	24	1242	57
L204	82	1339	506	24	1342	113	24	1342	109	24	1339	97
L207	84	1870	480	25	1983	98	25	1984	95	25	1976	102
L21	84	1381	589	25	1321	228	25	1300	227	25	1311	200
L210	84	1547	445	25	1519	138	25	1474	156	25	1528	97
L212	82	1760	470	24	1834	83	24	1834	83	24	1834	87
L213	32	1304	160	9	1304	17	9	1304	17	9	1304	17
L217	84	1308	316	25	1308	74	25	1306	74	25	1306	72
L219	84	1720	614	25	1721	184	25	1793	134	25	1784	135
L223	84	1725	513	25	1722	213	25	1745	185	25	1722	211
L226	84	1672	744	25	1662	358	25	1673	361	25	1752	352
L228	84	1323	691	25	1446	264	25	1441	245	25	1377	297
L229	76	1413	492	22	1413	97	22	1414	97	22	1493	124
L23	84	1664	740	25	1562	458	25	1656	477	25	1679	426
L230	84	1556	592	25	1584	149	25	1527	154	25	1697	156
L232	84	1596	587	25	1603	132	25	1600	155	25	1665	154
L234	84	1848	747	25	1743	324	25	1861	265	25	1820	275
L235	84	1653	419	25	1657	103	25	1657	106	25	1657	113
L236	84	1587	325	25	1558	100	25	1587	108	25	1568	95
L238	84	1210	424	25	1202	191	25	1201	189	25	1201	188
L24	84	1521	463	25	1555	147	25	1555	145	25	1523	143
L240	84	2004	812	25	1991	230	25	2113	217	25	2022	316
L241	84	1790	999	25	1817	511	25	1827	503	25	1825	537
L242	84	1144	219	25	1144	60	25	1144	60	25	1144	59
L243	84	1521	479	25	1636	78	25	1611	75	25	1521	74
L244	84	1566	394	25	1564	82	25	1529	82	25	1564	85
L245	84	1659	589	25	1660	111	25	1657	111	25	1657	127
L246	84	1276	484	25	1245	116	25	1245	115	25	1293	120
L248	84	2146	618	25	2152	104	25	2144	107	25	2257	122
L249	84	1255	473	25	1281	92	25	1258	89	25	1281	97
L25	84	1627	638	25	1675	258	25	1539	231	25	1544	251
L250	84	1607	408	25	1607	108	25	1606	96	25	1607	106
L251	18	447	71	4	447	2	4	447	2	4	447	2
L252	84	2198	657	25	2209	125	25	2203	117	25	2198	129
L253	84	1670	593	25	1682	196	25	1682	195	25	1670	206
L254	84	1553	590	25	1551	160	25	1549	157	25	1551	167
L255	84	1428	566	25	1406	124	25	1425	127	25	1485	114
L256	84	1786	561	25	1704	242	25	1705	245	25	1715	208

L257	84	1709	595	25	1734	180	25	1642	174	25	1649	163
L26	84	1506	413	25	1494	93	25	1494	88	25	1494	101
L260	84	1487	342	25	1455	105	25	1455	88	25	1455	87
L261	84	1365	446	25	1306	150	25	1306	148	25	1302	155
L262	84	1313	262	25	1308	62	25	1308	61	25	1310	64
L263	84	2905	1084	25	3102	405	25	3097	441	25	2968	400
L265	82	1219	372	24	1219	70	24	1219	67	24	1218	92
L266	84	1433	644	25	1413	260	25	1420	253	25	1384	278
L268	84	2061	549	25	1983	90	25	1983	90	25	2057	112
L270	84	2272	329	25	2285	145	25	2285	140	25	2271	177
L273	80	1259	342	24	1259	85	24	1259	82	24	1259	95
L274	84	1713	426	25	1713	81	25	1649	76	25	1653	98
L275	84	1790	746	25	1777	120	25	1897	110	25	1790	142
L277	84	1312	399	25	1362	76	25	1362	72	25	1361	71
L278	84	1553	453	25	1551	84	25	1551	101	25	1606	82
L279	84	1635	684	25	1614	320	25	1662	302	25	1628	291
L28	84	1425	920	25	1417	491	25	1486	477	25	1434	516
L280	84	1305	614	25	1281	219	25	1341	272	25	1297	276
L281	84	1294	601	25	1234	331	25	1325	299	25	1313	307
L282	84	1198	318	25	1211	61	25	1211	60	25	1211	62
L283	84	1786	574	25	1773	144	25	1771	148	25	1746	141
L284	84	1221	487	25	1168	112	25	1224	131	25	1217	155
L285	78	1619	406	24	1600	125	24	1600	123	24	1601	127
L286	84	1506	431	25	1510	84	25	1509	81	25	1505	76
L287	84	1111	506	25	1078	308	25	1088	309	25	1233	202
L288	84	1613	566	25	1604	237	25	1602	241	25	1596	220
L289	84	1420	419	25	1411	106	25	1429	94	25	1420	84
L29	84	1525	527	25	1490	142	25	1513	134	25	1533	114
L291	84	1373	484	25	1356	170	25	1386	166	25	1386	186
L292	84	1316	621	25	1322	233	25	1322	232	25	1299	213
L293	84	1194	345	25	1155	169	25	1142	168	25	1218	158
L294	84	2149	914	25	2042	523	25	2095	543	25	2039	544
L295	84	1502	402	25	1508	92	25	1508	89	25	1508	116
L296	84	1250	505	25	1256	76	25	1242	75	25	1274	86
L297	82	1033	436	24	1138	104	24	1061	120	24	1033	124
L298	84	1413	502	25	1322	121	25	1416	83	25	1408	112
L299	84	1403	525	25	1468	152	25	1490	148	25	1395	144
L3	84	1263	499	25	1256	177	25	1255	173	25	1263	172
L300	84	1352	417	25	1326	97	25	1340	97	25	1334	97
L302	84	1522	540	25	1582	141	25	1584	130	25	1556	147
L305	84	1659	443	25	1658	81	25	1658	81	25	1659	82
L307	80	1104	444	24	1091	118	24	1091	108	24	1091	119
L308	84	1792	648	25	1838	220	25	1835	218	25	1745	243
L309	84	1499	451	25	1443	213	25	1433	189	25	1444	208
L31	84	1635	536	25	1738	105	25	1645	107	25	1628	111
L310	84	1499	339	25	1389	110	25	1389	104	25	1389	114
L311	80	1427	492	24	1508	118	24	1508	118	24	1415	99
L312	84	1451	425	25	1444	127	25	1444	131	25	1444	132
L313	84	1240	310	25	1236	89	25	1235	121	25	1238	92
L314	84	1250	489	25	1235	124	25	1236	122	25	1226	136
L315	84	1534	461	25	1563	164	25	1477	154	25	1546	140
L316	84	1720	693	25	1720	193	25	1734	176	25	1726	205
L318	84	1364	442	25	1411	111	25	1411	112	25	1363	114
L319	84	1275	472	25	1291	90	25	1291	90	25	1234	114
L320	84	1583	816	25	1610	271	25	1633	263	25	1636	304
L321	84	1518	635	25	1606	188	25	1519	148	25	1598	162
L322	84	1593	682	25	1702	231	25	1585	193	25	1572	177
L323	80	1501	528	24	1496	130	24	1432	126	24	1432	124
L324	84	1418	550	25	1338	236	25	1451	177	25	1396	238
L325	84	1633	494	25	1616	85	25	1616	89	25	1629	88
L326	84	1588	421	25	1560	188	25	1560	195	25	1556	153
L327	80	1310	357	24	1179	125	24	1225	81	24	1189	105
L328	84	1524	592	25	1486	139	25	1481	117	25	1486	121
L329	84	1720	806	25	1826	225	25	1662	229	25	1866	222

L33	84	1734	695	25	1606	269	25	1882	205	25	1725	245
L332	84	1265	569	25	1260	220	25	1281	196	25	1270	255
L333	84	2601	1155	25	2492	395	25	2671	375	25	2654	376
L334	84	1702	668	25	1721	211	25	1705	190	25	1839	186
L336	84	1233	368	25	1285	120	25	1256	137	25	1254	138
L337	84	1123	306	25	1123	77	25	1123	77	25	1123	66
L338	84	1512	629	25	1457	218	25	1460	227	25	1503	205
L339	84	1440	538	25	1411	161	25	1410	169	25	1350	167
L34	84	1551	472	25	1559	65	25	1551	60	25	1459	71
L340	84	2088	1012	25	2102	350	25	2053	368	25	2202	320
L341	84	1303	757	25	1325	461	25	1349	425	25	1334	461
L344	84	2210	748	25	2433	231	25	2261	196	25	2358	208
L346	84	1772	472	25	1726	175	25	1714	175	25	1711	204
L348	84	1760	594	25	1915	113	25	1898	98	25	1729	177
L349	84	1499	563	25	1498	88	25	1498	83	25	1498	85
L35	84	1797	866	25	1891	409	25	1901	410	25	1859	428
L350	84	1668	455	25	1665	115	25	1665	101	25	1666	115
L352	84	1485	444	25	1503	201	25	1607	181	25	1484	202
L353	84	2468	705	25	2434	169	25	2465	152	25	2431	181
L354	84	1683	736	25	1679	298	25	1726	301	25	1679	280
L356	84	1509	660	25	1532	138	25	1531	145	25	1535	159
L358	84	1901	459	25	1924	148	25	1883	72	25	1864	150
L365	84	1361	743	25	1289	377	25	1364	343	25	1271	388
L366	84	1613	341	25	1620	121	25	1620	127	25	1612	127
L367	84	1548	637	25	1506	227	25	1525	213	25	1567	204
L368	84	1320	447	25	1320	72	25	1315	72	25	1320	73
L369	84	1448	599	25	1440	198	25	1440	154	25	1448	199
L37	84	960	314	25	971	77	25	969	70	25	971	72
L370	84	1382	519	25	1361	120	25	1384	86	25	1382	124
L372	84	1594	500	25	1714	127	25	1620	120	25	1685	102
L373	84	1776	594	25	1867	109	25	1866	108	25	1866	110
L374	84	1497	755	25	1481	425	25	1530	399	25	1475	396
L375	84	1580	648	25	1573	134	25	1576	127	25	1579	154
L376	84	1256	286	25	1253	58	25	1255	58	25	1252	60
L379	84	2156	709	25	2004	314	25	1969	318	25	1979	317
L38	84	1333	364	25	1332	116	25	1332	106	25	1333	120
L380	84	1532	649	25	1605	196	25	1605	193	25	1605	201
L381	84	1373	444	25	1377	104	25	1377	103	25	1377	103
L382	84	1853	668	25	1867	201	25	1850	236	25	1832	172
L384	84	1422	302	25	1410	82	25	1407	80	25	1410	81
L386	84	1810	723	25	1895	333	25	1820	322	25	1865	330
L387	84	1814	237	25	1811	51	25	1814	54	25	1814	61
L39	84	1439	473	25	1387	107	25	1387	100	25	1389	117
L390	84	1247	522	25	1281	138	25	1217	157	25	1219	148
L391	84	2025	658	25	2291	103	25	2291	101	25	1999	207
L392	84	1431	537	25	1434	141	25	1418	141	25	1417	200
L394	84	1640	646	25	1630	272	25	1630	264	25	1643	270
L395	84	1912	480	25	1842	121	25	1877	114	25	1857	132
L396	84	1487	619	25	1519	192	25	1487	203	25	1598	176
L397	84	2080	616	25	1949	189	25	1949	188	25	1877	224
L398	84	1280	437	25	1258	128	25	1258	122	25	1256	146
L4	84	1467	753	25	1520	202	25	1580	196	25	1495	184
L400	84	1644	591	25	1566	280	25	1584	282	25	1618	283
L401	80	1423	413	24	1431	94	24	1430	94	24	1394	103
L402	84	1340	598	25	1324	168	25	1304	189	25	1340	152
L403	84	1193	350	25	1193	69	25	1206	70	25	1236	71
L404	84	1755	565	25	1572	162	25	1589	156	25	1572	148
L405	84	1380	408	25	1289	108	25	1363	103	25	1289	106
L406	84	1605	654	25	1606	229	25	1617	234	25	1524	262
L407	84	2242	956	25	2090	492	25	2012	462	25	2013	492
L408	84	1767	463	25	1772	109	25	1650	121	25	1762	108
L41	84	1304	245	25	1304	51	25	1304	51	25	1304	54
L410	84	1426	728	25	1468	375	25	1434	372	25	1435	361
L411	78	1537	327	23	1485	61	23	1485	59	23	1485	65

L412	84	1755	615	25	1672	200	25	1727	210	25	1690	186
L413	70	1294	225	20	1294	40	20	1294	36	20	1293	51
L414	84	1318	311	25	1261	89	25	1276	72	25	1313	114
L415	84	1484	338	25	1482	76	25	1484	66	25	1484	80
L416	84	1567	754	25	1570	155	25	1570	153	25	1571	157
L418	84	2022	752	25	1927	288	25	1983	258	25	1966	290
L419	84	1373	310	25	1366	46	25	1366	44	25	1365	58
L420	84	1583	547	25	1575	105	25	1539	115	25	1517	128
L421	84	1704	710	25	1707	187	25	1644	207	25	1660	225
L422	84	1355	243	25	1356	74	25	1349	71	25	1355	74
L423	80	1255	467	24	1255	105	24	1255	104	24	1255	106
L424	84	1692	468	25	1692	118	25	1687	111	25	1692	123
L425	84	1380	366	25	1387	87	25	1387	86	25	1388	88
L426	84	1887	435	25	1850	131	25	1876	110	25	1848	119
L428	80	1241	434	24	1199	185	24	1155	176	24	1208	171
L429	84	1413	519	25	1475	189	25	1456	203	25	1468	194
L430	84	1466	441	25	1466	83	25	1455	86	25	1455	85
L431	76	1372	385	22	1409	113	22	1427	124	22	1410	120
L432	84	1543	454	25	1571	84	25	1707	83	25	1704	75
L433	84	1451	501	25	1446	124	25	1445	118	25	1465	108
L434	84	1519	472	25	1451	93	25	1505	91	25	1507	95
L435	84	3085	907	25	3068	336	25	3090	312	25	3116	324
L436	76	1569	475	21	1621	81	21	1646	93	21	1635	93
L437	84	1366	375	25	1347	112	25	1347	112	25	1348	110
L438	84	1696	666	25	1619	359	25	1512	334	25	1598	355
L439	84	1358	400	25	1372	87	25	1371	87	25	1389	85
L440	84	1369	477	25	1368	125	25	1368	120	25	1380	132
L441	84	1454	528	25	1427	132	25	1444	136	25	1433	140
L442	82	1595	498	24	1584	122	24	1584	124	24	1584	128
L443	84	1413	514	25	1407	194	25	1359	191	25	1363	180
L447	84	2310	787	25	2527	197	25	2527	197	25	2578	176
L448	84	1709	621	25	1694	199	25	1610	198	25	1743	198
L449	74	932	142	22	932	78	22	932	79	22	927	98
L450	84	1490	453	25	1490	153	25	1550	126	25	1492	151
L46	84	1900	274	25	1900	55	25	1900	55	25	1900	53
L48	84	1567	568	25	1496	158	25	1499	175	25	1579	152
L49	84	1917	539	25	1823	255	25	1667	237	25	1879	233
L5	84	1058	417	25	1045	107	25	1045	106	25	1058	105
L50	84	1526	600	25	1733	136	25	1692	133	25	1692	121
L51	84	1224	338	25	1221	49	25	1226	50	25	1229	56
L53	84	1643	348	25	1643	69	25	1643	69	25	1643	75
L54	84	1754	463	25	1711	79	25	1711	80	25	1723	96
L55	84	1959	331	25	1959	47	25	1959	43	25	1959	50
L56	84	1519	578	25	1533	178	25	1533	173	25	1545	227
L57	84	1901	694	25	1948	215	25	1916	214	25	1843	222
L58	84	1796	511	25	1732	140	25	1798	144	25	1734	125
L59	84	2069	772	25	1984	176	25	1966	168	25	2071	149
L6	84	1684	435	25	1723	97	25	1724	97	25	1724	108
L60	84	1682	494	25	1681	89	25	1681	86	25	1669	113
L61	84	1667	536	25	1802	145	25	1803	144	25	1802	147
L64	84	1239	397	25	1239	101	25	1239	97	25	1237	93
L67	84	1564	425	25	1570	172	25	1566	166	25	1566	183
L69	84	1536	406	25	1589	120	25	1535	113	25	1591	120
L7	84	2262	727	25	2333	156	25	2126	146	25	2323	133
L70	84	1644	639	25	1681	283	25	1592	259	25	1627	253
L71	84	1464	694	25	1439	415	25	1432	405	25	1464	377
L72	84	1714	458	25	1594	307	25	1575	307	25	1545	305
L73	84	1402	469	25	1441	185	25	1437	172	25	1435	199
L74	84	1383	716	25	1239	447	25	1293	435	25	1315	434
L75	84	1713	597	25	1713	118	25	1714	134	25	1651	142
L77	84	1469	595	25	1345	194	25	1345	186	25	1481	185
L78	84	1690	994	25	1828	462	25	2038	469	25	1743	499
L79	84	1785	726	25	1879	295	25	1757	340	25	1790	361
L8	84	2576	645	25	2566	234	25	2566	218	25	2670	257

L80	84	1492	538	25	1500	245	25	1589	200	25	1532	202
L83	84	2100	692	25	2123	262	25	2125	254	25	2068	284
L84	84	1432	600	25	1441	109	25	1441	113	25	1582	120
L85	84	1124	415	25	1146	134	25	1149	150	25	1148	137
L86	84	1268	383	25	1278	81	25	1278	80	25	1281	79
L87	84	1614	660	25	1615	190	25	1635	171	25	1596	200
L89	84	1226	264	25	1220	61	25	1220	60	25	1226	67
L9	84	1823	776	25	1849	187	25	1849	176	25	1884	197
L91	84	1571	283	25	1561	54	25	1561	54	25	1561	54
L93	84	1593	366	25	1628	169	25	1628	168	25	1532	207
L94	78	982	379	23	1007	207	23	971	226	23	1033	222
L95	84	1395	298	25	1312	164	25	1312	165	25	1343	147
L97	84	1119	486	25	1124	161	25	1124	140	25	1123	174
L98	84	2130	954	25	2131	557	25	2160	499	25	2201	526
L99	84	1684	721	25	1646	245	25	1618	237	25	1707	246
Average	83.02	1564.24	530.65	24.69	1561.96	168.08	24.69	1562.20	163.76	24.69	1563.16	168.92

161

162 **Table S3 – Alignment Statistics across Data Types.** PI sites are the number of Parsimony

163 Informative sites.

164

Allopolyploid	Data Type	Parameter	Mean	Lower 95% HPD	Upper 95% HPD
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	lnL	-679943.918	-680077.843	-679805.337
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	lnL	-643104.864	-643205.417	-643004.169
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	lnL	-627201.4897	-627284.005	-627119.895
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	lnL	-634366.8596	-634447.562	-634285.619
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	phi_h<-t	0.504627	0.436357	0.6569
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	phi_h<-t	0.428202	0.38779	0.466869
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	phi_h<-t	0.45668	0.413564	0.498812
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	phi_h<-t	0.454166	0.404159	0.503595
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	tau_4r	0.005085	0.002027	0.006392
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	tau_4r	0.006077	0.005563	0.006601
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	tau_4r	0.005468	0.004957	0.005985
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	tau_4r	0.006045	0.005425	0.006716
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	tau_5t	0.000414	0.000306	0.000508
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	tau_5t	0.000438	0.000311	0.000565
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	tau_5t	0.000584	0.00029	0.000839
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	tau_5t	0.000797	0.000533	0.001021
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	tau_6s	0.000549	0.000449	0.000654
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	tau_6s	0.000628	0.000515	0.000752
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	tau_6s	0.000599	0.000467	0.00073
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	tau_6s	0.00086	0.000684	0.001035
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	tau_7h	0.000393	0.000272	0.000502
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	tau_7h	0.000223	0.000141	0.000318
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	tau_7h	0.000428	0.000001	0.000652
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	tau_7h	0.00076	0.000496	0.001001
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_1Dgol	0.000457	0.000349	0.000557
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_1Dgol	0.000523	0.000398	0.00065
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_1Dgol	NA	NA	NA
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_1Dgol	NA	NA	NA
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_2Dlud	0.001426	0.001173	0.001692
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_2Dlud	0.001778	0.001502	0.002049
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_2Dlud	0.002253	0.001694	0.002852
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_2Dlud	0.002607	0.002004	0.003215
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_3Dcel	0.06869	0.039693	0.110449
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_3Dcel	0.001671	0.00115	0.002215
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_3Dcel	0.082217	0.000998	0.238998
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_3Dcel	0.280123	0.059426	0.655403
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_4r	0.034482	0.02827	0.038914
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_4r	0.046163	0.041346	0.051188
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_4r	0.047823	0.042752	0.053267
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_4r	0.045486	0.040775	0.050331
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_5t	0.014404	0.010708	0.023365
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_5t	0.009078	0.007762	0.010407
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_5t	0.008391	0.006775	0.010079
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_5t	0.009492	0.007309	0.011678
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_6s	0.00937	0.004944	0.011689
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_6s	0.008004	0.007046	0.008927
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_6s	0.005645	0.004806	0.006514
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_6s	0.007863	0.006482	0.009268

<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_7h	0.006979	0.00102	0.01363
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_7h	0.013604	0.003842	0.030768
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_7h	0.018192	0.000882	0.061998
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_7h	0.01308	0.00098	0.040084
<i>D. celsa</i>	phased	theta_8h	0.009827	0.00103	0.028194
<i>D. celsa</i>	genotype	theta_8h	0.008762	0.001611	0.021348
<i>D. celsa</i>	consensus	theta_8h	0.011238	0.001026	0.032819
<i>D. celsa</i>	pickone	theta_8h	0.008789	0.000953	0.024666
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	lnL	-585944.0596	-586075.806	-585813.001
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	lnL	-569990.0378	-570099.939	-569876.18
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	lnL	-545586.866	-545676.096	-545500.869
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	lnL	-551530.8014	-551618.271	-551439.823
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	phi_h<-t	0.471758	0.395516	0.550255
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	phi_h<-t	0.522176	0.463008	0.582006
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	phi_h<-t	0.544687	0.483768	0.603035
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	phi_h<-t	0.555426	0.495655	0.612902
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	tau_4r	0.007279	0.006759	0.007789
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	tau_4r	0.007384	0.006867	0.007921
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	tau_4r	0.005939	0.005381	0.00647
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	tau_4r	0.006621	0.006051	0.007211
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	tau_5t	0.001513	0.001243	0.0018
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	tau_5t	0.000882	0.000671	0.001099
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	tau_5t	0.000658	0.000389	0.000948
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	tau_5t	0.000835	0.000461	0.00121
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	tau_6s	0.002178	0.001886	0.002479
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	tau_6s	0.002077	0.001726	0.002428
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	tau_6s	0.001621	0.001298	0.001959
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	tau_6s	0.00197	0.001608	0.002339
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	tau_7h	0.001485	0.001204	0.001766
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	tau_7h	0.000472	0.000297	0.000641
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	tau_7h	0.000371	0.000004	0.000795
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	tau_7h	0.000569	0.000002	0.001084
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_1Dexp	0.005722	0.00492	0.006574
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_1Dexp	0.004458	0.003668	0.005297
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_1Dexp	0.004865	0.003196	0.006632
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_1Dexp	0.006904	0.004535	0.00949
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_2Dint	0.005479	0.004995	0.006006
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_2Dint	0.006216	0.005602	0.00682
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_2Dint	0.005006	0.004248	0.005769
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_2Dint	0.006481	0.005484	0.007474
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_3Dcam	0.014223	0.012595	0.015867
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_3Dcam	0.00149	0.001085	0.001913
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_3Dcam	0.02878	0.001191	0.077795
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_3Dcam	0.064045	0.001128	0.18099
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_4r	0.094151	0.086343	0.102337
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_4r	0.097957	0.089609	0.106504
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_4r	0.100146	0.091742	0.109043
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_4r	0.094327	0.08638	0.102448
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_5t	0.024663	0.021883	0.027395

<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_5t	0.028104	0.024631	0.031627
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_5t	0.025404	0.021655	0.029276
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_5t	0.032728	0.027807	0.037801
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_6s	0.009647	0.008377	0.01091
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_6s	0.00871	0.007435	0.009976
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_6s	0.006315	0.005204	0.007401
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_6s	0.007617	0.006301	0.008929
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_7h	0.008955	0.003843	0.015733
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_7h	0.01218	0.003548	0.025771
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_7h	0.010725	0.002701	0.02266
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_7h	0.020217	0.003158	0.047095
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	phased	theta_8h	0.003633	0.000684	0.009084
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	genotype	theta_8h	0.008383	0.001784	0.019821
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	consensus	theta_8h	0.014371	0.001025	0.040727
<i>D. campyloptera</i>	pickone	theta_8h	0.016487	0.000951	0.055001
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	lnL	-844606.6632	-844796.987	-844414.86
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	lnL	-691785.3795	-691893.399	-691677.283
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	lnL	-678628.4082	-678713.278	-678537.146
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	lnL	-692474.636	-692564.019	-692383.155
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	phi_h<-t	0.332922	0.106005	0.840279
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	phi_h<-t	0.254936	0.189996	0.320312
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	phi_h<-t	0.757824	0.584269	0.912797
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	phi_h<-t	0.86745	0.795465	0.925204
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	tau_4r	0.002857	0.002272	0.003331
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	tau_4r	0.002318	0.001958	0.002679
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	tau_4r	0.001409	0.001057	0.001781
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	tau_4r	0.002236	0.001715	0.002714
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	tau_5t	0.001317	0.000783	0.002431
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	tau_5t	0.000201	0.000134	0.000267
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	tau_5t	0.000074	0.000006	0.000188
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	tau_5t	0.00006	0.000001	0.000355
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	tau_6s	0.000689	0.000425	0.001107
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	tau_6s	0.000626	0.000448	0.000818
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	tau_6s	0.00036	0.000021	0.000775
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	tau_6s	0.000419	0.000013	0.000784
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	tau_7h	0.000632	0.000272	0.001107
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	tau_7h	0.000178	0.000123	0.000234
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	tau_7h	0.00003	0	0.000099
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	tau_7h	0.000047	0	0.000332
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_1Dgol	0.000654	0.000481	0.000895
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_1Dgol	0.000647	0.00049	0.000801
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_1Dgol	NA	NA	NA
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_1Dgol	NA	NA	NA
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_2Dcri	0.089117	0.056512	0.118635
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_2Dcri	0.002887	0.002158	0.003631
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_2Dcri	0.010955	0.001595	0.027525
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_2Dcri	0.008274	0.000919	0.033657
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_3Dcli	0.759117	0.216175	1.676369
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_3Dcli	0.001077	0.000795	0.001357

<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_3Dcli	0.006674	0.001076	0.017165
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_3Dcli	0.021785	0.00076	0.103124
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_4r	0.058278	0.054253	0.062397
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_4r	0.050855	0.047451	0.054283
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_4r	0.052871	0.049326	0.056406
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_4r	0.054709	0.051096	0.05864
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_5t	0.034865	0.00224	0.049053
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_5t	0.013239	0.010949	0.015634
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_5t	0.031073	0.022006	0.040398
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_5t	0.144179	0.095216	0.208439
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_6s	0.059369	0.007337	0.085735
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_6s	0.021697	0.016597	0.027023
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_6s	0.006642	0.001357	0.014338
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_6s	0.003367	0.00098	0.006741
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_7h	0.06851	0.000624	0.286324
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_7h	0.015401	0.004426	0.033165
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_7h	0.006885	0.000938	0.017984
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_7h	0.005872	0.000996	0.014861
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	phased	theta_8h	0.036053	0.000575	0.14961
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	genotype	theta_8h	0.004783	0.000799	0.012033
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	consensus	theta_8h	0.006054	0.001033	0.015025
<i>D. clintoniana</i>	pickone	theta_8h	0.00891	0.00097	0.024465

165

166 **Table S4 – Posterior Means and HPDs for Parameters from MSci Model 5.** Summary

167 statistics are based on combined posteriors of four independent chains for each data type for

168 each triplet. Parameters correspond to subscripts shown in Supplementary Figure S2.

169

Phasing	$h^\dagger$	<i>D. campyloptera</i>		<i>D. celsa</i>		<i>D. clintoniana</i>	
		-Pseudo InL	Δ PInL	-Pseudo InL	Δ PInL	-Pseudo InL	Δ PInL
Consensus	0	21.10	NA	28.16	NA	6.42	NA
	1	0.10	21.00	0.06	28.10	0.16	6.26
	2	0.10	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.16	0.00
Genotype	0	19.71	NA	24.43	NA	5.67	NA
	1	0.52	19.19	0.13	24.30	0.23	5.44
	2	0.52	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.23	0.00
Phased	0	14.15	NA	16.15	NA	4.39	NA
	1	0.07	14.08	0.18	15.97	0.15	4.24
	2	0.07	0.00	0.18	0.00	0.15	0.00
Pick One	0	18.16	NA	27.17	NA	5.79	NA
	1	0.21	17.94	0.55	26.61	0.15	5.64
	2	0.21	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.15	0.00

[†]Maximum number of reticulation events allowed. Does not require that h reticulations be found. Species at the top are the allopolyploid involved in the tests with three taxa.

170

171 **Table S5 – PhyloNetworks Results for Analyses of *Dryopteris* Data.** Results are for

172 analyses of all target-enrichment loci. Improvement to the negative Pseudo-loglikelihood score

173 are the previous h minus the current h . The choice of h that reflects the last improvement

174 greater than 2 was used for networks in Figure 6.

175

176

Phasing	$h^\dagger$	-Pseudo lnL	Improvement
Phased	0	720.90201	NA
	1	498.069854	222.83
	2	362.691802	135.38
	3	262.496633	100.20
	4	262.46153	0.04
	5	262.116879	0.34
	6	262.116875	0.00
Consensus	0	866.100725	NA
	1	624.106594	241.99
	2	485.718856	138.39
	3	0	485.72
	4	0	0.00
	5	0	0.00
	6	0	0.00
Genotype	0	896.671312	NA
	1	657.892974	238.78
	2	511.265498	146.63
	3	408.720801	102.54
	4	408.715613	0.01
	5	402.685359	6.03
	6	399.109218	3.58
Pick One	0	892.403129	NA
	1	678.22724	214.18
	2	555.232715	122.99
	3	455.461673	99.77
	4	406.99917	48.46
	5	396.792253	10.21
	6	396.766129	0.03

†Maximum number of reticulation events allowed. Does not require that h reticulations be found. Although the pseudo-loglikelihood improved for some models as h increased, the maximum number of reticulations recovered by any network for that data type is indicated in bold.

177
178 **Table S6 – PhyloNetworks Results for Analyses of all North American *Dryopteris*.** Results
179 are for analyses of all target-enrichment loci. Improvement to the negative Pseudo-loglikelihood
180 score are the previous h minus the current h . The number of reticulations indicated in bold were
181 used for bootstrapping.
182